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1. RECORDS MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SERVICE DELIVERY: A CASE OF ACADEMIC REGISTRAR'S DEPARTMENT AT THE ALL-SAINTS UNIVERSITY LANGO

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Abstract

The delivery of services in an academic department relies on its ability to manage records through good records management practices. This study was carried out to examine the records management practices in the Academic Registrar's Department (ARD) of All Saints University Lango (ASUL) and how they impact service delivery. The objectives were to examine the types of records kept, records management practices, and the associated challenges and recommend strategies for improvement. The study used a case study design with a qualitative approach that was employed in the study. Purposive and convenient sampling was carried out on the study participants. Data was collected from 13 respondents, including three registrars, two records staff, two secretaries, one IT support team, and five students. This was done through interviews, participant and direct observation, and document analysis. The study found that ARD generated various records, including academic results, programs, reports, and individual student files. The study found that the records storage conditions were poor, and records files were packed and retained on the office table and the floor. Records staff, Secretaries, and Registrars managing academic records had limited records management knowledge and skills, which affected service delivery. The study recommended that ASUL employ professional records management staff to manage academic records and train all ARO staff on records management practices to ensure effective service delivery.

Keywords: Records management, academic records, ephemeral value, records continuum, recordkeeping

1 Introduction

The day-to-day operations of any successful university depend entirely on its records management practices (Simwaka, 2022). As academic departments provide services, records continue to grow, and therefore, academic departments need consistent and coherent record management practices and procedures to successfully manage records throughout their lifecycle (Simwaka, 2022). Records management practices include the processes of systematically managing records, including identifying, classifying, filing, storing, archiving, and controlling the destruction of records (Tadaferua & Omehia, 2022).

Effective management practices make records easy to access and retrieve (Touray, 2021). Easy to track and protect from unauthorised alteration and deletion (Muhammad et al., 2021; Touray, 2021). Accurate and proper records in the academic registrar's department can be kept appropriately (Dano & Ibrahim, 2021; Ifenaike & Olatokun, 2021). Ineffective records management practices lead to inefficient staff time and poor decision-making due to failure to access the right records (Allison, 2021). Misplacement of files and loss of records in academic departments (Falolo et al., 2022). A required record will not be easily retrieved if the practices are ignored, and searching for a particular record will also take much time (Barigye et al., 2022). Such a condition has a great potential to hamper service delivery in a university and compromise the attainment of transparency and good governance (Musembe, 2016).

Scholars such as (Allison, 2021; Mwanyungu, 2019; Otieno, 2021; Sanwine, 2020; and Shonhe & Grand, 2018) all agreed that records management enhances service delivery in academic institutions. They discovered that the services provided by academic departments included the admission of new students, conducting examinations, verifying student results, maintaining archive academic reports, preparing and issuing transcripts, preserving students' registration forms, providing class schedules and timetables, filing and maintaining academic records (Allison, 2021; Sanwine, 2020).

The ASUL academic registrar's department generates records as students are admitted, during continuous registration, and as transcripts are issued. However, records are difficult to access when needed by the students and staff (All Saints University Lango, 2020a). The report further indicated that information relating to different activities carried out in the ARD was not produced on time, there were no proper and adequate ways to keep the incoming and outgoing records and heaps of unfiled records are a common site in all offices at ASUL. Against this background, this study was carried out to examine the records management practices at the Academic Registrar's Department.

2 Theoretical framework

A theoretical framework is a foundational review of existing theories as a roadmap for developing arguments for research work (Calder et al., 2023). The records life cycle theory and the records continuum guided this study. These theories are brought together under an integrated recordkeeping framework with the same goal to guarantee the reliability, authenticity, and completeness of records regardless of format (Matlala & Maphoto, 2020). The purpose of using the two approaches is to provide a common understanding, consistent standard unified best practice criteria, and interdisciplinary approaches to recordkeeping and archiving processes for both paper and digital records (Evans et al., 2017; Frings-Hessami, 2022).

The basic concept of this life theory is that every record progresses through three phases: a record is created, is used and maintained, and is dispositioned (either by destruction as a record of ephemeral value or by transfer to national archives as a record of enduring value) (Tadaferua & Omehia, 2022). Meanwhile, the continuum concept ensures a consistent and coherent process of record management throughout the life of records, from the development of recordkeeping systems through the creation and preservation of records to their retention and use as archives (Evans et al., 2017).

With the prevalent of paper records in academic institutions, as reported by previous researchers (Adu, 2014; Otieno, 2021; Sanwine, 2020), the records life cycle alone would only give the essential guide to the management of records, but the Records Continuum was also helpful to analyse the records that existed in the electronic format.

Records creation and receipt is the initial step in records management (Ameyaw & Frempong-Kore, 2020). Academic records are created as students fill in their forms, i.e., biodata forms, communicate via emails, and through registration, for example, in exams, class attendance, and so forth (Adu, 2014; Musembe, 2016). They are also received from internal and external sources and identified, such as memos, correspondences, emails, students' admission letters, examination results, and transcripts, among others (Sanwine, 2020). Records are captured into an appropriate recordkeeping system after creation to be readily available for retrieval and use (Otieno, 2021).

Filing and indexing is the second step in managing academic records (Allison, 2021). This involves having a records file plan and procedures to enhance the filing practice. A file plan specifies how records are to be organised and managed, for example, allocating file reference numbers, retention periods, and other instructions for managing the records (Allison & Otuza, 2017). Records-filing procedures require first checking whether the appropriate file on which the record is supposed to be placed exists (Sanwine, 2020).

If it does not exist, a new file is created and titled accordingly; then a folio reference number is assigned to each record to differentiate it from other records on the file (Wilkins, 2021).

Filing may be organised centrally, whereby all the files of an institution are kept and controlled in one room (Allison, 2021). Meanwhile, an institution may adopt a decentralised file storage system where the records are stored in many locations, and each department files its record (Adu, 2014). This is also known as categorising, classifying, or unitising records (Dasmani, 2019). Classification schemes and file plans ensure a coherent and consistent arrangement of records and subsequently form the basis for effective record filing, retrieval, retention, and disposition (Mahama, 2017; Otieno, 2021). They are essential in assigning security status to users, including restricting access to some classes of records as a legal requirement (Simwaka, 2022).

According to Annoh (2019), having a records inventory is another vital management practice that universities always adhere to. He conceded that a completed inventory provides a picture of what records are physically stored, the volume of storage, or how they are classified for future use and retrieval. A records inventory is vital in gaining control of a university's number of records created.

Simwaka (2022) noted that records maintenance and use are essential aspects of records management practices and cannot be ignored. Barigye et al. (2022) clarified that records maintenance involves storing and retrieving records for future use. (Nwaomah, 2017) viewed that to determine a records storage strategy and to ensure that the strategy is adequate, he suggested the following guiding questions:

- Where and how do you store your active records?
- Where and how do you store your inactive records?
- Do you have a “records protection” procedure in the event of litigation?
- How are you storing your electronic records?
- What is the environmental condition of your storage facilities?

When a record is retrieved for use, it is also essential to track it till it is returned to its designated storage area (Dasmani, 2019; Wilkins, 2021). Tracking records practices will help identify who had accessed the record, when they accessed that information, and whether any action was taken or changes made to the record (Iliyasu & Abdullahi, 2017).

Records disposition is thus the least practised part of managing academic records. It is a stage that determines whether a record should be destroyed or retained permanently by the university's legal or disposal procedure.

This chapter included a review of the literature and the theories that informed the study, all based on the research objectives. It showed that the types of records generated depend on the activities conducted in the Academic department; it also demonstrated that the records management practices followed by the Academic department, such as records creation, capture, filing, records storage, providing security to the records could either improve or hamper service delivery. While the extant literature provided a theoretical foundation for the study, little has been known about records management practices and service delivery at All Saints University Lango (ASUL), ARD. To fill this knowledge gap, this study examined the applied records management practices and their impact on service delivery at ASUL.

3 Research methodology

The researcher used a case study design because the researcher wanted to examine the records management practices in a real-life context. The study's target population comprised 22 respondents, including three records staff, three academic registrars, three secretaries, three IT support teams, and ten students (All Saints University Lango, 2020b).

This study used purposive sampling to select eight respondents, including three records staff, two Academic Registrars, two secretaries, and one IT staff. The main reason was because they were involved in creating and using records in their daily activities. Therefore, as stated in the research objectives, they were required to give their views about the records management practices and how they affect service delivery at ARD, the challenges faced, and the strategies that can be used to streamline them.

The IT support team was required to provide information concerning the technology at the various stages of the records' lifetime. This included ascertaining information on the information management systems currently in use, the structure of the databases, and the measures followed for records creation, records classification, establishing retention rules, and access controls or security rights for records created and managed with IT systems.

Convenient sampling was used to select five students who queued at the academic registrar's office. The researcher used convenient sampling on the students because they were found queuing at the ARD to access the services differently. The researcher used convenient sampling to get information on how quick it was to get services at the ARD. For example, records were consulted first when needing an academic transcript.

The data collection tools consisted of the interview guide, documentary review guide, and observation guide. In-depth interviews were held with the records staff, Academic registrars, secretaries, IT Support team, and the students.

The study also analysed documents such as the student's admissions policy (2021), the Academic Registrars Staff Profile (2021), the Students' Registration Procedures, the ARD Strategic plan (2020-2025), the Annual year report, and the university policy documents to ascertain the context and the environment of ASUL within which the study for records management practice was being done. The documents were also analysed for the obtainability of evidence of the practices for managing records at the Academic Registrar's Department ASUL.

The study was purely qualitative. The collected data was sorted and analysed using content analysis, guided by various themes, concepts, patterns, and categories aligned with the study's objective. Data was coded and summarised to make a meaningful interpretation.

4 Findings and Discussion

The findings presented in this section include the records management practices implemented from creation to disposition. Participants' responses on service delivery were also included.

4.1 Response rate

The statistics in Table 1 summarise the respondents' responses according to their positions at work in ARD.

Table 1: Response rate by category of respondents

S/N	Category/position	Target population	Actual respondents	Percentage %
1	Records staff	3	3	100
2	Academic Registrars	3	2	67
3	Secretaries	3	2	67
4	IT supports Team	3	1	33
5	Students	10	5	50
	Total	22	13	100

Table 1 shows that out of 13 targeted respondents that participated in the study, the majority (100%) were records staff, followed by 2(67%) Registrars, 2(67%) Secretaries, 1(33%) IT supports staff and 5(50%) students. The findings revealed a high participation rate among the records staff and poor response from the IT support team. The participation of many records staff, registrars, and secretaries implies that the university relies on this staff category to perform its records management functions. They had concerns about managing and carrying out records management functions to ensure service quality.

4.2 Duration in service

The information regarding work experience was sought. The participants were asked to indicate the length of time they had been in service of the ARD. Table 2 provides the details.

Table 2: Description of the respondent's years of service (n=8)

Duration	No. of respondents	Percentage %
15years and above	5	63
5-15years	2	25
0-5years	1	12
Total	8	100

Table 2 shows that most respondents had worked for more than 15 years in the ARD at ASUL. As seen from Table 3, 5(63%) had worked for 15 years and above, while 2(25%) had experience of 5 years, followed by 1(12%) who had served below five years. The data confirms that the respondents had worked long enough to be adequately informed about the records management issues at the Academic Registrar's department.

Participants were asked about the practices of record creation at the ARD. It was revealed that the records were created and received through the admissions process, issuing of transcripts and certification of documents, examination, academic verifications, students' progress reports, receipts of admissions letters, and book registers. Furthermore, they included minutes of meetings and curriculum activities.

During the interview, the participant explained that records details are captured during creation:

"We capture details such as file titles, file types, and dates created at this stage. As time passes, files get older, and more details are added to the file cover, including the volume number and date for closure."

Observation revealed that records are created through the process of applications, admissions, enrollment, matriculation, and research reports, which was in line with (Adu, 2014; Musembe, 2016), who found out that academic records are created as students fill in their forms, that is biodata forms, emails, and through registration for example in exams, class attendance, and so forth. However, it was observed that some of the record files lacked index and abstract details, making it hard to capture and track evidence of file movement. This is contrary to (Otieno, 2021), who revealed that when records are created or received, it has to be captured in an appropriate medium after the creation so that they are readily available for institutional support to ensure that the records created are the ones needed and not non-essential records (Otieno, 2021).

Regarding records classification, the participants noted that ARD uses a subject classification system, with records assuming order by subject. However, observations showed that the files shelved were not classified and that the records management staff needed to have a good memory of where the records files are located. This contradicted the findings by (Nwaomah, 2017), who argued that one of the essential elements in gaining control of a university's records is classification and held the view that academic institutions can categorise their records according to classes, forms or grade levels, subject areas or by individuals as well as unitise according to clients, names of projects, or locations.

Furthermore, concerning records maintenance and use, the participants shared that some files were kept on shelves and cabinets, and others were being heaped on the floor and the desks at the workstations. The records packed in boxes looked decrepit and weedy; the shelves were open without locks. When inquired about such practices, one of the participants stated:

“We normally packed some of the files in boxes and bags to ensure they are not lost. We would have kept them in cabinets and shelves, but they are insufficient. We provide shelves and cabinets, but many departments have reported they are insufficient as the records keep growing.”

Observation also revealed that the ARD lacked enough space and thus ended up using available bags and space on the floor to retain some of the records; however, the majority of the staff used the academic records daily to meet the administrative needs of the university and to support decision-making, among other purposes. This finding did not concur with a report by Aminu and Aliero (2019), who stressed that a good storage program should provide proper storage space and tools such as shelves, vaults, and cabinets to store records and to ensure the records are protected and secured from both environmental factors and intruders.

Participants were how regarding records disposition. The study established that the practices for disposing of records were not correctly followed. This originated from the fact that the academic Registrar’s office had no policy specifying the procedures for retaining and disposing as reviewed from the available documents that support records management in the ARD, as one of the participants remarked.

“Indeed, we do not yet have a conventional procedure in managing the records; there are no records and information policies that are yet established, and we have not got complaints...and I appreciate this conversation.”

When interviewed, the IT team revealed that some of the records in their databases were archived in the cloud, as they lacked enough computers and Internet infrastructure to make their work easy. An IT staff member said:

“There is much work the IT team does. Thus, it would be on the part of the records staff to adequately take part, research, and come up with appropriate records and information manual that will guide in all these practices.”

The findings revealed that the record management staff had limited knowledge of records and archives disposition and how to devise a disposition schedule. This was contrary to (Sanwine, 2020), who asserted that records management staff are ignorant of their duties because they did not observe the basic tenets of good records management.

To ascertain feedback from students on service delivery and records management practices. The services were always slow and ineffective as they lined up and spent the whole day being served, especially when processing their transcripts and certificates and verifying their results.

This affected the students, as one of them observed that her marks were noted missing, yet she had sat for the paper, which was later verified, but almost missed graduating.

Observations revealed that the records were hard to retrieve and always took long for students to be served because the records shelved lacked classification numbers and were difficult to sort. This revealed a gap in service delivery at ARD. The above finding was appalling because (ISO, 2011) highlighted that records management practices provide the mechanism whereby a university can account for its decisions and actions and retain corporate memory for effective service delivery. Therefore, there is a call for the ARD to manage its records comprehensively and responsibly to provide quality services to its stakeholders.

5 Conclusion

The findings revealed that although records were vital to running the ASUL academic registrar's office, the Academic registrar department did not have well-defined records management procedures. It was noted that no member with a records and information professional background was assigned the responsibility of managing records in the academic registrar's department. Generally, there was no specified position of a records manager in the university. As a result, records practices were left to the discretion of the secretaries and the records management staff, who had no qualifications or records management training. Therefore, the records management practice in the academic registrar's department was inadequate and needed to be streamlined. This jeopardised service delivery at the academic registrar's office. Records management practices are required at the Academic Registrar's office ASUL as a basis for managing academic records because they are vital for effective service delivery. Gaps that needed to be addressed were identified to minimise the risk of not having records management practices that enhance quality service delivery.

6 Recommendations

The study made the following recommendations:

- In consultation with records management experts, the Academic Registrars should identify and transfer all archival records to a designated storage area and ensure that only records with archival value are maintained.
- The records management staff and the Academic Registrars should also be required for adequate, reliable, and secured storage materials and equipment such as shelves, cabinets, files, and appropriate boxes to facilitate proper storage of ARD records. This will help to solve the problem of keeping records and files in old sacks and polythene bags and piling them on the floor, which exposes them to damage and the risk of losing valuable information.
- The Academic Registrar should also organise training for secretaries, records staff, and IT support personnel by inviting records professionals, experts, and consultants, such as from the Uganda National Records Centre and Archives (UNRCA), records managers, and staff from other universities, to train all staff in the practices of records creation, maintenance, use, and disposition.
- The academic registrar's office should also train records management staff and continue training them in records management to keep abreast with new professional developments.
- Qualified record managers should be recruited to manage the university's records.
- The academic registrar should budget for a robust ICT infrastructure to generate and maintain electronic records. This will mitigate dependency on paper-based records and reduce the storage space challenges experienced in maintaining paper-based records.

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